

OPTICAL DETECTORS

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Abstract: Fiber optic communication heavily relies on optical detectors, predominantly semiconductor devices like PIN diodes and avalanche photodiodes (APDs). These detectors, akin to diodes in circuit structure, must operate under reverse bias to function as detectors. This thesis views the pivotal role of semiconductor optical detectors, specifically PIN diodes and avalanche photodiodes (APDs), in fiber optic communication systems.

Like optical sources, the optical detectors used in fiber optics are almost exclusively semiconductor devices in the form of PIN diodes and avalanche photo diode (APD) detectors. From a circuit perspective, these are again diodes that like any other diode (including laser diodes or LEDs) can be forward or reverse biased. However, for them to act as detector, they must be reverse biased. A PIN diode can operate with a very low reverse bias. This makes the PIN diode attractive because it can be operated as an element within a standard electronic circuit that runs at a low supply voltage of say 3.3 V. Figure 1. shows a simple detector circuit. The output of the detector is a current that is proportional to the light power received by the detector. Thus, the detector can be considered as a light-controlled current source. A transimpedance amplifier (TIA) converts the photocurrent generated by the detector to a voltage

Fig. 1. Simplified detector using PIN diode or APD

APD detectors are not very different from a circuit point of view. However, they require a much higher reverse bias voltage to operate. Currently low-voltage APDs require at least 30–40 V of reverse bias. Moreover, the required

optimal reverse bias voltage for an APD varies with temperature. As the temperature rises, the reverse bias applied to the APD must also increase to maintain the gain of the APD constant. Because of these complications, APDs are harder to use and more care must be taken in designing them. They are also more costly in terms of both the APD itself and the additional required support circuitry. However, APDs have a big advantage that makes them attractive for high-end receivers: unlike PIN detectors, an APD detector provides inherent current gain. This additional gain directly translates to improved performance. Typically an APD can work with a fraction of the optical power needed for a similar PIN diode, and this means longer links can be supported with an APD receiver.

Использованная литература:

- [1] G. Keiser, Optical Fiber Communications, McGraw-Hill, New York 1999
- [2] Y. D. Chung et al., "A 60-GHz-band analog optical system-on-package transmitter for fiber radio communications," Journal of Lightwave Technology, Vol. 25, pp. 3407–3412, 2007
- [3] J. X. Cai et al., "Long-haul 40 Gb/s DWDM transmission with aggregate capacities exceeding 1 Tb/s," Journal of Lightwave Technology, Vol. 20, pp. 2247–2258, 2002
- [4] C. H. Cox, Analog Optical Links, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2004

